

EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERACTIVE TEACHING APPROACHES IN ORAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF GRADE 6 PUPILS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of interactive approaches in oral communication in Grade 6 English at Abanon Central School, San Carlos City during the School Year 2018-2019. In this study, the control group obtained a mean score of 21.44 with a mean score percentage of 53.60 while the experimental group obtained a mean score of 23.05 with a mean percentage score of 57.63. Both control and experimental groups performed relatively low as revealed by the pre-test result. The pre-test and post-test of the control group indicates an improvement of their level of performance in oral communication English 6. There is also a significant difference in the performance between the pre-test and post-test. The computed t-value is 20.470 which is greater than the critical t-value of 2.030 at 0.50 level of significance with degree of freedom of 35. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference in the performance of the experimental group in the pre-test and post-test. The computed t-value of 25.756 which is greater than the critical value of 2.032 at 0.5 level of significance with degree of freedom of 34. Thus, there is a significant different in the performance of the experimental group who were exposed to interactive teaching approaches.

Keywords. interactive teaching approach, oral communication, English, effectiveness, traditional teaching approach

1 Introduction

The general consensus of the Government Academic Industry Network (GAIN), Inc., (2018) is that the Philippines is superior to its neighboring countries in terms of English Proficiency. This shows that the advantage English-speaking country is greater than other countries such as Singapore and Thailand. In fact, Filipinos have always been known as one of the top English-speaking citizens in Asia as well as in the whole world. We are highly regarded because of our adaptability to other languages especially the English language. But the test of times cannot deny the fact that we have always been facing difficulties in the oral communication skills of learners as revealed by their performance nowadays.

Naturally, the problem does not magically disappear after graduation. A 2012 poll of businessmen in the American Chamber of Commerce in the Philippines rated English skills of the Filipino workforce as deteriorating. To cite a specific figure, only 16 percent of the nursing applicants passed the US Test of spoken English. Furthermore, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) Philippine Human Development Report said that aspiring Filipino teachers have poor English language skills, and that out of all the subjects in their licensing exams, they score the lowest in English. Reports of the erosion of the quality of Filipinos' English have convinced President Gloria Arroyo's administration that a rapid and extensive deterioration could take place.

In the research conducted by Southville Foreign University and Hopkins International Partners, Inc. in 2017 showed that Filipino university graduates averaged a Common European framework of Reference of Language (CEFR) grade of B1, lower than the CERF B2 proficiency target set for high school graduates in Thailand and Vietnam. The CEFR B1 average for Filipino university graduates is compared to the proficiency of 5th and 6th grade students in native English-speaking countries such as the US and United Kingdom.

Today's education set-up, pupils are taught in their native language till the third grade; where there is minimal time for utilization of English as a medium of instruction. English is only used as a third language for instruction. Most elementary grade English teachers have been facing difficulties in orienting pupils in English and see pupils find it real difficult to express themselves in English both oral and written.

Of the problems that beset the present Philippine education, perhaps the most relevant is the quality of inputs, processes and outcomes. These problems are reflected on the support provided by the government on education sector, the abrupt changes in the systems of education, the lack of proficient skills needed for students to meet the standards of higher level of schooling, the deficient qualification of teachers and the lack, imprecision and glaring mistakes in instructional materials and textbooks.

Among other things, these studies attributed the low achievement scores of students to quality of teachers. The latest National Achievement Test Results of Grade 6 in English recorded an average of 41.1% level of performance. What could not be negated however, is the concern of the quality of instruction and even the language of instruction, an issue that continues to be debated despite the overwhelming empirical evidence that learning and instruction in the early grades is best facilitated using *lingua franca* as the medium of instruction.

The researcher who happened to be an English teacher for the past 5 years observed that most of his learners are having difficulties in communicating themselves orally in English and so he decided to conduct this study. For as a teacher, the researcher believes that a teacher is one of the primary movers who have the task to improve the oral communication of Grade 6 learners in English. The researcher intended to utilize and measure effectiveness of certain interactive teaching approaches in improving the oral communications of learners in English.

2 Review of Related Literature

Filipinos have always been dubbed as one of the best English-speaking races in the world. A Filipino can adapt easily to other cultures around the world because of his ability to interact with foreign lands easily. But as time passes by, this ability slowly deteriorates and this is being affected by how pupils in school communicate themselves orally. The crucial part of it is expressing themselves in English effectively and clearly.

curriculum needs to be updated regularly, not only to incorporate knowledge but also to adopt the changing environmental social, technological and global contexts. Teachers must possess the 21st Century Skills to include the use of technology in teaching. Bernardo (2014).

According to Nunan (2012) it seems that practitioners of English language teaching are prone to embrace new fashions in teaching without really going into what we are letting ourselves and our students in for. In the past, there have been many methods that held up to be the answer to language teaching, each of these methods being an attempt to react to a perceive change in the needs of society at large, and, by implication, the changing needs of students. Speech is the tool that leads to mutual understanding and appreciation; hence, it is important to employ and develop these God-given faculties. (Ballesteros 2007).

Oral communication anxiety is one of the most studied phenomena among western communication researchers. So much attention has been given to this phenomenon that almost every aspect of it has been explored and written about. Yet, despite it being extensively studied the case is quite different in the Philippine setting. There is still a dearth of research data on Filipinos considering oral communication anxiety's overwhelming impact on speakers. (Del Villar, 2006).

In the study conducted by Villaber and Gonzaga (2018), they recommended that the students should be given more enrichment activities prior to the oral examination schedule to exercise their public speaking abilities and enrich communication skills. They should be asked with varied questions to explore oral communication strategies which they could employ to give more answers and give motivation. Their performance as well should be assessed through constructive criticism to improve their communication skills.

The study of Aliyu (2017) highlights the benefits of collaborative learning which include developing students' oral communication skills, social skills and academic skills. He also stressed the need to adopt collaborative learning method in our classrooms in order to develop students' oral communication skills. In the study of Juan and Lasatin (2016), they recommended that to provide opportunities for the students to reduce their oral communication apprehensions level in English and to improve their academic performance, the teacher educators are encouraged to focus not just on listening activities as this would not be enough to help students overcome their apprehensions

Students should be provided specific learning opportunities of Oral Communication Skills in the classroom through activity-based teaching in which students should be given tasks in groups and pairs. It would develop both accuracy and fluency. They gradually realize their own mistakes and it leads towards self and peer correction process. It was found that using teaching strategies such as demonstrations, role plays and discussions were effective ways to improve students' oral proficiency. Thus, this study argues that until and unless teachers

and school principals take responsibility of students' learning and provide opportunities to students to practice language in classroom, the real purpose of language teaching will not be achieved. (Alam, 2013).

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study made use of quasi-experimental research. It is a quasi-experimental research because the researcher conducted the study to evaluate the effectiveness of a treatment. Experimental research provides a systematic and logical method for answering the question. This study also made use of random sampling using fish bowl method in determining the two groups of study. The researcher also made use of toss coin method in determining the control and experimental group respectively

3.2 Subjects of the Study

The subjects of the study are the Grade six (6) learners handled by the researcher in English at Abanon Central School during the school year 2018-2019. Since there are four (4) sections in Grade 6 at Abanon Central School, the researcher made use of fish bowl method and the two (classes) that were drawn are Grade 6-JT and Grade 6-MP. When the two classes were selected, the researcher made use of toss coin method and determined that Grade 6 JT is the experimental group and 6 MP as the control group.

3.3 Statistical Treatment of Data

To attain valid and reliable results from the data gathered, appropriate statistical tools were used. To answer sub-problems 1 and 3, Mean Scores and Mean percentage Scores (MPS) were used to obtain, determine and further describe the learners' performance in the tests. To answer sub-problems 2 and 5, t-test for independent samples with uncorrelated means was employed. To answer sub-problem 4, t-test for independent samples with correlated means was employed.

This study made use of Statistical Procedure for Social Sciences (SPSS) Program in processing, interpreting and determining the desired statistical measures and answer all the questions in the study.

4 Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Performance of the Grade 6 learners in English in the Pre-test Results

Table 1 shows that the control group obtained a mean score of 21.44 with a mean percentage score of 53.60 while the Experimental group obtained a mean score of 23.05 with a mean percentage score of 57.63. It also reflects that the experimental group performed slightly better than the control group. The mean percentage scores of both control and experimental groups are way below the Department of Education's prescribed mastery level of 75%.

Table 1. Pre-test Result of the Control and Experimental Group

Group	Mean	Mean Percentage Score (MPS)	Standard Deviation
Control Group	21.44	53.60	2.38
Experimental Group	23.05	57.63	2.87

4.2 Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Pre -Test

Table 2 shows that the respondents registered their mean difference of 1.61 which reveals that there is a difference in the performance of the two groups in the pre-test and that the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the performance of the two groups in the pre-test is hereby rejected because the computed t-value of 2.574 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.955 at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 2. Test of Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Pre-Test, N=71

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significance	Decision
Control Group	21.44	1.61	2.574	*Significant	Ho is Accepted
Experimental Group	23.05				

4.3 Performance of Grade 6 Learners in English in the Post - Test

Table 3 shows that the learners in the control group obtained a mean score of 28.63 in the post test. The mean percentage score (MPS) of this group exposed to traditional instruction is 71.58. The learners in the experimental group obtained a mean score of 34.28 in the post test in English Grade 6 and the computed mean percentage score is 85.70.

Table 3. Post-test Results of the Control and Experimental Group in English 6, N=35

Group	Mean	Mean Percentage Score (MPS)	Standard Deviation
Control Group	28.63	71.58	1.83
Experimental Group	34.28	85.70	1.99

4.4 Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Pre -Test

Table 4 reveals the significant difference in the performance of the control and experimental group in oral communication in English. It could be gleaned from the table that the control group obtained a mean score of 28.63. On the other hand, the experimental group obtained a mean of 34.28. Meanwhile, the mean difference of the two groups is 5.65. The computed t-value of 12.315 is relatively greater than the critical value of 1.955 which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the performance of the two groups in the post-test. Note that there is also an improvement in the performance of the control group but improvement is significantly greater in Experimental Group.

Table 4. Test of Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Post-Test, N=71

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significance	Decision
Control Group	28.63	5.65	12.315	*Significant	Ho is rejected
Experimental Group	34.28				

4.5 Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control Group in the Pre-test and Post test

Table 5 shows that the pre-test and post-test of the control group indicated an improvement on their level of performance in Oral Communication in English. It can be observed that there is an increase in the mean score of the control group with a mean difference of 7.19. Hence, it may be inferred that there is a significant difference in the performance between the pre-test and post-test.

Table 5. Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control Group in the Pre-test and Post-test, N=36

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significance	Decision
Control Group	21.44	7.19	20.470	*Significant	Ho is rejected
Experimental Group	34.28				

4.6 Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control Group in the Pre-test and Post test

Table 6 shows that the results of the pre-test and post-test of the experimental group also showed improvement in the learners' performance as exposed to interactive teaching approaches. It can be gleaned from the same table that the experimental group obtained a mean difference of 11.23. hence, it can be inferred that the experimental group showed significant difference between the pre-test and post test scores. This reflects that there was a significant improvement in the performance of this group in their oral communication skills after they were exposed to interactive teaching approaches. The group's mean percentage score of 85.70 is also above the prescribed 75 % mastery level standard set by the Department of Education.

Table 6. Significant Difference in the Performance of the Experimental Group in the Pre-test and Post-test, N=35

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significance	Decision
Control Group	23.05	11.23	25.756	*Significant	Ho is rejected
Experimental Group	34.28				

It can be deduced that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significance difference in the performance of the grade 6 learners in the oral communication skills in English as exposed to interactive teaching approaches in the pre-test and post-test is hereby rejected.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

The performances of the control and experimental groups in the pre-test are low. There is a significant difference in the performance of the control group and the experimental group in the pre-test. The level of performance of the experimental group is higher than the control group based on the post test results. There is a significant difference in the performance of the control and experimental group in the post-test and the experimental group performed higher than the control group after using the interactive teaching approaches. There is a significant difference in the performance of each of the two groups in the pre-test and post-test.

Teachers should conduct regular evaluation on oral communication to the Grade 6 learners.

Elementary teachers should be encouraged to employ interactive teaching approaches to help improve the oral communications of learners in English. Interactive teaching approaches should be used not only in English but in all subject areas as well by all teachers. Teachers should explore and use varieties of approaches that can lead improvement of learners in oral communications.

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